

Mentorship as a professional development tool: usage of technology as an
integrated part of the International Baccalaureate curriculum

Mentoring within the teaching profession

Case Study

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Introduction

Professional development and education are necessary components of modern society for every individual. It enables professional progress and career prosperity.

Generally speaking, the abandonment of the traditional understanding of education pushes boundaries and opens the door to societal progress. Education and a quality upbringing can be achieved only by building a high-quality educational system with highly educated professional staff. In addition to initial teacher education, it is vital to maintain continuous professional development, renewal, and supplementation of knowledge and skills. It is not only beneficial for teachers but also provides students with opportunities to acquire competencies.

The 21st-century teacher is considered a bearer of change, ready for continuous learning and personal achievement. Thus, a teacher becomes a driver of learning and a helping hand in each student's development. However, many comparative studies show that the quality of education provided by homeroom and subject teachers is significantly influenced by the foundation of education and the knowledge of educational sciences, particularly the psychology of learning and teaching. Changing the system of teacher education is a fundamental precondition for the successful transformation of the school system in line with the requirements of modern society. Different participants and users of the education system emphasise the importance and inevitability of profound structural changes in education.

The traditional approach is still dominant in curriculum design and educational practice. It is perceived as a limiting factor in modern society's orientation towards establishing a culture of knowledge and learning.

In addition to analysing teacher education through a systemic lens, this paper will present a comparison between the public Norwegian and International educational systems.

Following that, the first part of the paperwork will present the professional competences of teachers—the definition and importance of lifelong learning and its essentials according to the European standards, which include general knowledge and skills necessary for the personal and professional development of each individual.

In the second part of this paper, the professional development of teaching staff in public and the international system will be elaborated, in addition to the initial teacher education program. All institutions that provide education address the provision of professional development. This paper discusses their role and importance in the continuing education of teaching staff from a teacher's perspective.

Professional development motivation is a crucial factor in this context. Professional development is a complex process characterised by the permanence of the acquisition, enrichment, and monitoring of new knowledge, and the strengthening of abilities and skills. Abilities and attitudes are necessary for a wide field of teaching roles. Given the vital role teachers play in supporting students' achievement, improving teachers' professional development is of great importance to overall changes in the education system. The factors influencing teachers' motivation for professional training, including length of service, knowledge and use of a foreign language, school environment, length of study, and average grade point, will be emphasised in this part of the paper. Changing the teacher's role in the classroom (where he or she serves as a mentor, with an emphasis on the activity and students' independence in their studies) is crucial for motivating professional development, as is the need to individualise instruction and to discover students' needs and differences.

Nowadays, not as many teachers emphasise the strong need for information literacy as was the case ten years ago. Information literacy is developed through teachers' work experience, a consequence of technological progress in the previous twenty years in the field of informatics and technology. In the following text, technological literacy will be considered as part of professional development.

Competences of educators

Competence, i.e. teacher competence, is a systematic connection of knowledge, abilities, values and motivation on a functional level. The complexity and importance of the teaching profession for the development of the individual and society are reflected in the ability to mobilise, use, and integrate existing competencies, as well as in the acquisition and improvement of new competencies. As abilities, competencies include a degree of self-reasoning and a responsible attitude towards the social and work environment. They are developed and upgraded and include theoretical knowledge, understanding, and practical application of how to act and live with others in a social context.

Teachers' professional competencies are of great importance because the necessary knowledge, skills, and habits of students are shaped by educators' work. According to Grimen, the homogeneity of teaching is defined as the first dimension of the degree of knowledge (Grimen 2008:72). A knowledge base is homogeneous if all its elements originate from the same scientific discipline or field of knowledge.¹ In the current educational system, teachers are given new tasks, and they appear in a new role. Their freedom of action is expanding, and their competencies are growing. The teacher follows the given concepts less and less, presents ready-made solutions, and increasingly acts as a practitioner and researcher who is critical of existing problems and can take a creative approach to solve specific problems. Teachers are required to be open to changes in the paradigms of education, including the courses, content, forms, and methods of teaching and learning. They are faced with a new concept aimed at lifelong learning for both teachers and students.

Teachers' pedagogical competence can be divided into eight dimensions: personal, communicative, analytical (reflective), social, emotional, intercultural, developmental and problem-solving skills.

The fundamental factors of a teacher's competence are empathy, respect for students, understanding, flexibility, friendliness, calmness, patience, fairness, objectivity, consistency,

¹ Grimen, Harald. 2008. "Profesjon og kunnskap" in A.Molander and L.I. Terum (ed.), *Profesjonsstudier*. Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, p.71-86.

professional ethos (taking responsibility for the success of each student) and the ability to choose appropriate behaviour depending on the situation. Communication competence encompasses social skills, including initiating, establishing, and maintaining dialogue with students through verbal and nonverbal symbols. In this way, creative and critical thinking, correct reasoning and culture of speaking and listening are developed. Social competence refers to the socially responsible behaviour required by the school, the acceptance of rules and customs, and the establishment of relationships with students, parents, colleagues, and the school administration. It is a comprehensive set of knowledge and skills that influence the acquisition of expected student social competencies, including cooperation, compromise, listening to and understanding others, respect for differences, anger control, nonviolent conflict resolution, working together, and encouraging friendships. Emotional competence is the ability of teachers to leave their life or career-related problems behind the classroom door and enter the classroom with a cheerful, smiling face. It includes an individual's ability to cope with their difficulties and to master relationships with others (empathy and social skills). Intercultural competence refers to knowing and respecting diversity - different beliefs, traditions, customs, lifestyles and their values. Developmental competence is based on the vision and mission of developing one's vocation. A competent teacher critically examines his/her pedagogical and didactic efficiency, and the holders in charge of teachers' continuous professional development are of particular importance here. Problem-solving skills refer to the responsible use of problem-solving strategies in different teaching situations, i.e., a positive attitude, realistic expectations, and recognition and response to individual students' needs.

Grimen argues that integrating these different elements of knowledge and skills significantly impacts the development of a healthy educational system.² The interdisciplinary approach is of immense importance for a broad understanding.

In the profession, the heterogeneous approach could be considered more effective, but as Grimen pointed out, the key question is: "Where do the elements of the profession's knowledge come from?"

² Ibid.

Professional development of educators and its forms

The general attitude among teachers is that after completing initial education and obtaining a diploma, they lack practical teaching skills and that there is a need for a better connection between theoretical and practical knowledge. Greater attention is paid to the practical aspect of initial education, cooperation between universities and schools where professional-pedagogical practice is conducted, i.e., the connection between initial education and the introduction to the profession.

Learning competence is defined as the ability to begin and continue learning, including the organisation of one's learning and the effective management of time and information. It includes learning about one's learning methods and needs, recognising opportunities, and the ability to overcome obstacles to achieve successful learning. It means acquiring and adopting new skills, including seeking and using advice. It directs those who learn to build on previous experiences, enabling them to use their knowledge and skills in new situations. Motivation and confidence in one's abilities play a significant role here.

As for the knowledge, skills and attitudes required for the competence, the awareness of one's learning strategies, the advantages and disadvantages of one's skills and qualifications, and the ability to seek educational and training opportunities or assistance are of the crucial importance for professional development; it is understood that the competence primarily requires necessary skills such as reading and writing, but also computing and ICT skills. Based on these skills, an individual can apply newly acquired knowledge and skills. Perseverance in learning, concentration over a long period, and critical thinking about the purpose and goals of learning are essential here. An individual should be able to organise their learning, seek advice, and evaluate their own work. One should have a positive attitude, grounded in motivation and confidence in continuous learning. The essential elements of a positive attitude are curiosity about opportunities to learn and to apply what has been learned in various life situations, and a desire to do so.

Learning for Life – International Baccalaureate Philosophy and Mission

Key competences for lifelong learning

Competencies, learning outcomes, and curriculum approaches are key topics in national education that have dominated pedagogical theory for several years. Through the social process of Europeanization, educational policies operate and change the framework of the national education system. For that reason, the need to determine basic competencies has developed, needed by society and the individual, in response to the challenges of modern globalisation. The European Commission has identified eight key competences for lifelong learning, and they represent the general knowledge and skills necessary for the personal and professional development of each individual.³

The importance of lifelong learning

Lifelong learning is a pedagogical concept that begins with the realisation that a person learns formally and/or informally throughout life. That learning is part of the inherent ability of people and an integral part of life practice and an essential component of its humanisation.⁴ Every upbringing and education is basically intentional and aimed at training an individual for a particular role in life or occupation. When the fact that more can always be given and done is acceptable, decisions are made to further develop the acquired knowledge and skills. Enabling a person to lead a quality life in the modern world order and society means that the individual should learn to think independently, freely, and critically; to act creatively; and to create new, high-quality knowledge throughout their life.

Lifelong learning encompasses formal, non-formal, and informal forms of education and seeks to integrate all phases of education across vertical and horizontal dimensions. Such education is characterised by its flexibility in terms of space, content, time, and manner of learning, and requires self-directed learning and the acceptance of different learning styles and strategies.

³ EUROPEAN COMMISSION. *COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Accompanying the document Proposal for a COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning*. Brussels, 17.1.2018

⁴ Spinoza's philosophy of immanence: "[...] an extended substance composed of an infinity of attributes that is purely **immanent** throughout nature" (Smith 2003: 18).

The key implications of lifelong learning are to change the understanding of education from schooling and to abandon the traditional belief that education is intended exclusively for children and young people. According to traditional belief, life is divided into two periods: childhood and adolescence, when one learns, and adulthood, when one works. Lifelong learning, including experiential learning for young people and adults, extends the concept of education to non-formal and informal adult education.

According to the International Baccalaureate programme, education is a tool to create a better world. The International Baccalaureate promote intercultural understanding and respect as an essential part of life in the 21st Century.

The mission is:

The International Baccalaureate® aims to develop inquiring, knowledgeable and caring young people who help to create a better and more peaceful world through intercultural understanding and respect.

To this end, the organisation works with schools, governments and international organisations to develop challenging programmes of international education and rigorous assessment.

These programmes encourage students across the world to become active, compassionate and lifelong learners who understand that other people, with their differences, can also be right.

Providing leading professional development is essential for professional growth. This is also something that the Norwegian National Curriculum strives for. These components include:

- support the professional growth of teachers and administrators
- improve classroom practice and student learning
- develop communities of lifelong learners.

Therefore, learning is no longer seen as a passive process of absorbing and memorising facts and data to be reproduced. Knowledge is not **transferred** from the teacher/professor to students; it is **constructed** in students' minds through prior experience and active learning methods.

Digitisation of the school system

Context of digital competence

Digital competence indicates the safe and critical use of information society technologies for work, leisure and communication. Basic skills support: using a computer to search, evaluate, store, produce, present, and exchange information, and participating in and communicating within collaborative networks over the Internet. This competence requires a good knowledge and understanding of the nature, role, and opportunities that information society technologies provide in everyday personal, social, and business life.

This applies to major computer actions, such as databases, storage, understanding the possibilities and potential dangers of the Internet, and handling information. It is necessary to have the ability to search, collect, and process information, and to use it critically and systematically, to assess its relevance and distinguish it from virtual connection recognition. Individuals should use ICT skills to support critical thinking, innovation and creativity.

Technology in the classroom

According to Blikstad-Balas, the biggest ICT problem in Norwegian classrooms today is not that the researchers in various studies want to bring students together on Facebook and various games in class, but that there are far too few situations where teachers provide real training in useful digital working methods in the subjects or situations. Digital tools should be used to redesign teaching so that their potential is utilised.⁵ Many teachers have expressed concern about the students doing something other than what they should do in class because they have access to the Internet. Responsibility for one's own learning, combined with free access to the Internet, does not automatically yield good results. There is a broad consensus that the goal of the Internet in schools is to support learning. There is no greater concern related to the fact that so few schools, most of which are private or international schools, can point to innovative, or at least systematic, professional use of digital technology with clear goals for professional learning.⁶

⁵ Blikstad-Balas, Marte. 2016. *Literacy i skolen*. Oslo: Universitetsforlaget

⁶ Blikstad-Balas, Marte. 2016 «Bedre skole» in *Bedre skole nr 2*. Utdanningsforskning.no

What must be clear to everyone involved in integrating technology into teaching and curriculum is that simply putting digital tools into schools is not the solution to incorporating technology into learning and teaching. For technology-assisted learning and teaching to be meaningful and useful, it is necessary to reconceptualise all three basics (learning, teaching, and technology) to extract the full combined meaning from them and to use all the possibilities.

As a design and technology teacher within the International Baccalaureate programme, I would like to highlight some observations.

Experience-based, it is necessary to distinguish between learning from technology and learning with technology. Learning from technology is based on the assumption that only the computer is a tutor that instructs how to do something, how to do a particular task. In contrast, the opposing assumption is that it is essential to learn with technology, in which the computer is just another tool for solving problems. A teacher who wants to integrate technology into the classroom knows how to present engaging, relevant projects, questions and problems for students, e.g. to find and present the latest discoveries related to the science that students are studying, research details of historical events, study the latest trends related to language teaching via the Internet. Software tools are very important for building a learning-friendly environment, and students use these new technologies to gather data, organise information, share what they have learned, and demonstrate their learning. This is a learning process of the 21st century, which the International Baccalaureate modern educational philosophy is based on.

In a technologically advanced classroom, the teacher's role shifts from information bearer to creator and supporter of the collaborative environment. The teacher leads students into a process in which they independently, through collaboration with others, create their knowledge. The role of students changes from a passive recipient of information into an active associate in teaching and work. The student defines goals, assesses his or her progress, and is responsible for his or her own learning. With the help of technology and computers, the student collects problems and organises their solution. Computers and the Internet can help teachers achieve good collaboration with other individuals, schools, and institutions. The usage of modern technologies enables the presentation of challenging, invisible, or unattainable phenomena in the classroom.

Mentorship and peer guidance within ICT and its integration in the curriculum and the classroom

In this part of the text, I will focus on mentorship and peer guidance for a colleague who struggles to implement ICT skills and knowledge in teaching and evaluating students' assignments.

An IT-literate person is someone who knows how to re-examine a problem, research a solution, think independently, and solve it with the help of technology. An information-literate person, from a large amount of information, successfully selects, re-examines, interrogates, analyses, and synthesises the information necessary to solve the problem.

As mentioned earlier in the text, implementing ICT into the International Baccalaureate curriculum is a huge part of the everyday life of each teacher and student working within this particular programme. According to Lauvaas and Handal, mentoring can be driven in different ways through various methods (Lauvaas & Handal 2019: 238). It could be in the form of a constructive conversation between colleagues, one-on-one. The more formal method would be for the leader to lead the conversation, or for a few people to present the problem and give a constructive argument based on their experience, qualifications, and knowledge.

Besides being a teacher, my role within the International Baccalaureate programme is to coordinate the IT platform for learning, assessment and reporting, called ManageBac, and to help colleagues with the implementation and maintenance of the system in teaching.⁷

In this case, where a female colleague struggles to implement a learning platform into her teaching methodology, I decided to use the one-on-one conversation as part of the mentorship process. Friendly approach, a conversation about a conversation, and a mirror-effect practical workshop are only a few of the methods used in this case, which will be elaborated further in the text. According to Gibbs (1988), reflection is a crucial part of the process that allows those who struggle to open up.

⁷ see <https://www.managebac.com/about>

The colleague belongs to the 65+ age group and is in the final phase of her career. In this phase, people usually experience anxiety and deal with repetitive thoughts in a manner that they are not good enough for this job, followed by low self-esteem.

I chose to follow Gibbs' scheme:

Image no.1. Phases in de-briefing conversation Gibbs (1988)⁸

⁸ Lauvaas, Per & Handal, Gunnar. 2019. *Veiledning og praktisk yrkesteori*. Oslo: Cappelen Damm Akademisk, p.238

- **Plan for guidance**

Starting point

- the guidance should be a meeting place for teachers' professional development, exchange of experience and reflection
- take as a starting point the challenges and needs of the one in need for mentoring, so that that person can influence the content of the supervision sessions. Define the need for topics and the real issues the person is facing
- contribute to the teachers' professional development and learning
- contribute to the best possible transition between education and working life
- contribute to a good start in working life
- contribute to security, well-being and mastery, which are fundamental for good development at work
- the guidance should be a meeting point to get in touch with others in the same situation

Mentor's responsibility

- Conduct formal individual tutoring sessions with the colleague, at least every other week. In addition, there will be informal conversations

Clarify mutual obligations and expectations between the colleague and the mentor

- Set up a predictable and long-term plan for the time of the mentoring sessions in collaboration with the colleague
- Be a reflection partner and support the new colleague in everyday work
- Takes extra responsibility for the colleague to feel comfortable and master her tasks

Responsibilities of the colleague in need for mentoring

- Clarify mutual obligations and expectations between the colleague and the mentor
- Set up a predictable and long-term plan for the time of the mentoring sessions in collaboration with the mentor
- The colleague in need for mentoring is responsible for meeting prepared for all supervision

- Participate actively and contribute to guides and gatherings becoming relevant for everyone
- Support the individual's professional development in group supervision (if any)

Topic

- Organization in everyday life - class management
- Annual planning, half-year plans, period plans
- New student in the class / new child in the group (ICT tutoring)
- Assessment work - assessment for learning
- Personnel management and collaboration with employees (interdisciplinary units and report cards in collaboration with other colleagues using ManageBac)
- Documentation and assessment
- Professional ethics
- Curriculum - subject renewal school/framework plan (new language acquisition guide-implementation in ManageBac)
- Send feedback

Learning in the workplace

According to Brookfield (1988), there are six principles of effective practice for facilitating adult learning: voluntary participation, mutual respect, collaborative spirit, action and reflection, critical reflection and self-direction.⁹ These six principles are parameters for the mentors' role.

As a novice in this role, I decided to follow the aforementioned principles. At first, the colleague declined to officially book the mentoring hours. She informally approached me several times, asking for help. In consultation with the leadership team, I accepted this method as valid and official. At first, the whole concept seemed chaotic, disorganised, and poorly communicated.

⁹ Jones, Marion. 2018. "The needs of mentors" in K.Smith and M.Ulvik (ed.), *Veiledning av nye lærere*. Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, p.127

The colleague could come and go with requests whenever she needed guidance and supervision about the ICT learning platform. Complaints about actions on the platform that the colleague has taken came from several sources (students, other colleagues, and the leadership team), e.g., double units created, incorrect attendance reports and assessment levels, shared documents not shared correctly, etc.

The anxiety occurred and rose. It reflected poorly on the communication from both sides. The colleague requested a written manual for the platform. Due to a lack of time and unpaid hours, this request was not rational. Therefore, I created a written manual for the platform's attendance section and video tutorials for teachers' use. Unsatisfaction from her side was obvious. The climax was reached during the workshop I provided for her when I used technical terminology. The colleague demonstratively shut down the computer system, saying that I spoke Greek to her in an ironic sense. Then, I realised that I was in the wrong all the time. Actually, language is a crucial tool in the mentorship process. We all see things from a different perspective. Our brains do not function in the same way. I belong to the younger generation born into a world of technology, one that has seen constant progress and innovation in this area. I should not expect that someone in the 65+ age group can understand IT terminology.

Rethinking and analysing the whole procedure was necessary. I created a plan presented earlier in the text. Including into consideration all aspects such as the previous history of the case, concretisation, the core of the problem, patterns, the views of others, the future, emotions, values and principles, general questions, I have informed the HR officer, as a person in charge, about changes I am going to make in the mentoring procedure. The plan was approved and presented to the colleague. Both sides agreed, and mentoring started its new phase. The sessions were driven once per week for an hour according to plan. Instead of creating manuals and tutorials, we found a common language in keeping a weekly journal and documenting all steps in the procedure. That includes all technical assignments and descriptions, along with drawings of each movement we made while using the platform. Small, easy, repetitive tasks were beneficial for her. I have noticed that she struggles with memorizing the steps. Easy steps and tasks created for her, supported with drawings, helped a lot in the process of memorizing.

After two months, the first results came into the light. The colleague became independent. She could completely achieve high results in everyday work assignments. After three months, the

colleague even discovered new, useful features on the platform and confidently suggested, during one of the meetings, the active use of those innovations by staff members. The suggestion was accepted, and the leadership team acknowledged her work and contribution.

The whole process in mentorship was supported with questions about the description of the problem, evaluation and analysis:

Can you please describe the situation/problem in detail?

What have you done so far? Please describe.

Can you please describe your feelings about this situation/problem? How do you feel when you cannot solve the technical issue?

What was good, and what was less good or bad in the mentoring process?

Was this situation difficult or maybe useful for you? Have you learned something?

Is there anything more I can do for you? Do you still need support, or might you need it in the future?

The evaluation process was based on mutual feedback about the approach and working progress. As mentioned earlier in the text, the negative feedback came when I realised my weaknesses and the mistakes I had made in the communication process. At the end of the mentoring process, we were both very satisfied with the results we achieved. She decides to refresh her knowledge and technical skills from time to time by taking workshops, but she mostly feels independent and can complete tasks successfully.

Conclusion

Digital competence in professional development programs is very important. Core competencies are essential for the personal and professional development of each individual, especially for those responsible for educational change, who play a key role in ensuring that students acquire the vital competencies for lifelong learning. Besides, it is important to improve the quality of professional development content and to include all the competencies an employee needs in the education system of modern society.

As a mentor in the professional development process, I have learned a few things to reflect on. First and foremost, it is crucial to find the positive side of the case. Such an approach builds a solid foundation to withstand all the challenges posed by reality, which both sides must face.

I learn how to listen every day. This is just one of the reasons why I consider listening skills to be the most important and greatest mentoring skill. The mentor simply has to listen to old things with new ears. Furthermore, listening involves a set of skills that require daily work. These are communication, facilitation, patience, understanding, tact, and negotiation skills. I have also learned how to ask the right questions, and that respect could be gained by giving respect.

However, it is important to consider the factors of stress and pressure in our social work environment and the pace of technological innovation. As information and communication technology developed and was applied across all social segments, the representation of digital competence in professional development programs also increased. However, it does not necessarily mean that anyone can follow the progress.

Therefore, a good mentor should be both a catalyst and a supporter of the lifelong learning process at each stage of the teacher's career.

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